

Participant Observation Guide for Hybrid Hackathons

The purpose of this protocol is to guide the observation of participating teams during a hybrid hackathon.

Category	Description	Observers should note
Participant interaction	Level of involvement of each participant.	<p>Hybrid influence: Interaction between in-person participants and between in-person and online participants.</p> <p>Take note of the non-verbal cues that show engagement. Examples: Shared screens, whiteboards or physical prototypes, chat messages and reactions, active working vs passive/disengaged.</p> <p>Codification: [Timestamp], [Participant/Team], [In-person/Virtual], [Interaction]</p>
Technology usage	Platforms, software, and hardware tools utilized by participants.	<p>Platform choices: Document which visible technologies are used for what purposes (communication, brainstorming).</p> <p>Technical difficulties: Make note of any technology-related interruptions or difficulties and how they are resolved.</p> <p>Codification: [Timestamp], [Participant/Team], [Issue], [Solution]</p>
Team roles	How participants work together in their roles	<p>Observe who takes on different roles in the team. What is their modality?</p> <p>Characteristics of leadership i.e., idea initiator/visionary, facilitator, presenter, note-taker etc.</p> <p>Note how tasks are distributed among team members and if the location (in-person or virtual) plays a role in these assignments.</p> <p>Codification: [Timestamp], [Participant/Team], [Team role], [In-person/Virtual], [Role objective]</p>

Category	Description	Observers should note
Task coordination	Task allocation, meetings and breaks.	<p>Synchronous vs. asynchronous work: Observe periods when the team works together in real-time and when they work separately. When participants separate, stick to the largest group in the same space.</p> <p>Time-zone coordination: How does the team navigate different time zones i.e., in scheduling meetings or meeting deadlines? Note possible hand-off procedures.</p> <p>Codification: [Timestamp], [Participant/Team], [In-person/Virtual], [Task allocation]</p>
Breaks and external interruptions	Instances where participants may encounter disruptions during teamwork.	<p>Disruptions affecting multiple teams (e.g., announcements/change in agenda, technical disruptions, participant “going home”, participant attrition etc.)</p> <p>Who/what is interrupting the participants, and why? What is the frequency of external interruptions?</p> <p>Is there any perceived impact of the interruptions on group dynamics and task completion?</p> <p>Codification: [Timestamp], [Participant/Team], [In-person/Virtual], [Interruption type], [Interruption outcome]</p>
Spatial dynamics	Organization and use of physical and virtual spaces for team activities	<p>Use of physical space: For in-person participants, observe the use of the physical space for collaboration. Use of provided resources (table arrangements, screens, whiteboards etc)</p> <p>Virtual participation interface: For virtual participants, note the “virtual space” setup, such as chat rooms, video conferencing layouts, and shared documents.</p> <p>Codification: [Timestamp], [Participant/Team], [In-person/Virtual], [Space type], [Space description]</p>